

New records of *Rhaphium* (Dolichopodidae, Diptera) from Russia

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Abstract

The paper presents new faunistic data for 28 species of *Rhaphium* from Russia and supplements the previous data on species distribution. New faunistic data is given for the following species: *Rhaphium albifrons* Zetterstedt, 1843, *Rh. antennatum* (Carlier, 1835), *Rh. appendiculatum* Zetterstedt, 1849, *Rh. basale* Loew, 1850, *Rh. boreale* Van Duzee, 1923, *Rh. caliginosum* Meigen, 1824, *Rh. commune* (Meigen, 1824), *Rh. confine* Zetterstedt, 1843, *Rh. dichromum* Negrobov, 1976, *Rh. discolor* Zetterstedt 1838, *Rh. dispar* Coquillett 1898, *Rh. elegantulum* Meigen, 1824, *Rh. fasciatum* Meigen, 1824, *Rh. fascipes* (Meigen, 1824), *Rh. flavilabre* Negrobov, 1979, *Rh. glaciale* Ringdahl, 1920, *Rh. latimanum* Kahanpää 2007, *Rh. longicorne* (Fallen, 1823), *Rh. monotrichum* Loew 1850, *Rh. nasutum* (Fallen, 1823), *Rh. nigribarbatum* Becker, 1900, *Rh. patellitarse* Becker, 1900, *Rh. richterae* Negrobov, 1977, *Rh. riparium* (Meigen 1824), *Rh. rivale* Loew, 1869, *Rh. suavis* Loew, 1859, *Rh. tripartitum* Frey 1913, and *Rh. umbripenne* (Frey, 1915). Seven rare species (*Rhaphium basale*, *Rh. boreale*, *Rh. confine*, *Rh. dispar*, *Rh. fasciatum*, *Rh. flavilabre* and *Rh. longicorne*) are recorded for the first time in one or two Russian regions. At present, there are 71 species in the genus *Rhaphium* known from Russia.

Keywords

Dolichopodidae, Rhamphinae, *Rhaphium*, Palearctic, Russia, species list

Introduction

The genus *Rhaphium* (Meigen, 1803), included in the subfamily Rhaphiinae, is composed of 200 species, considering unpublished data (Negrobov et al. 2013a; Grichanov 2017). O.P. Negrobov (1979) published the first revision of the Palearctic species of this genus; all presented species were described, and key to the Palearctic species was presented. The last key to the female species belonging to *Rhaphium* was provided in 2017 (Kleschevnikova and Negrobov 2017). In addition, a checklist of Dolichopodidae of Russia was supplemented by the current year faunistic records included 66 species of *Rhaphium* (Negrobov et al. 2013a).

The following three species were not included in genus *Rhaphium* for Russia (Negrobov 1979, 1986; Yang et al. 2006): *Rhaphium doroteum* Negrobov, 1979, described from the Irkutsk region and Primorye, *Rhaphium terminale igorjani* Negrobov, 1986 and *Rh. neolatifacies* Yang et Wang, 2006 described from Sakhalin Island. Then I.Ya Grichanov provided the new species for Russian fauna (*Rhaphium nigrum* (Van Duzee, 1923) from Chukotka Peninsula (Grichanov 2018).

The genus was revised for the Palearctic Region by Negrobov (Negrobov 1979) and nine species and one subspecies were reported from Russia: *Rhaphium terminale igorjani* Negrobov, 1986, *Rh. jamalense* Negrobov, 1986, *Rh. macalpini* Negrobov, 1986 and *Rh. neolatifacies* Yang et Wang, 2006, *Rh. jonrichardi* Negrobov et Grichanov, 2010, *Rh. brooksi* Negrobov, Barkalov et Selivanova, 2011, *Rh. subtridactium* Negrobov, Barkalov et Selivanova, 2011 and *Rh. sibiricum* Negrobov, Barkalov et Selivanova, 2011, *Rh. borisovi* Negrobov, Barkalov et Selivanova, 2012, *Rh. caucasicum* Negrobov, Grichanov et Selivanova 2013 (Negrobov 1986; Negrobov and Onishchenko 1991; Negrobov and Grichanov 2010; Negrobov et al. 2011, 2012, 2013b).

Material and methods

We examined the specimens from the collection of the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (ZISP) and the collection of Department of Ecology and Systematics of Invertebrates of Voronezh State University (VU). In addition, several specimens were examined from the collection of the Zoological Museum of Moscow State University (ZMMU).

Results

Material examined

New records of species of the genus *Rhaphium* in the Russian regions.

Rhaphium albifrons Zetterstedt, 1843

RUSSIA • 1 ♂; **Tuva Republic**, Ishti-Khem; 29 Jun. 1974; collector is not specified; ZISP RH2970.

Faunistic notes: Krasnoyarsk, Irkutsk, Khabarovsk and Leningrad Regions, Mor-dovia Republic, Altai and Primorye. Recorded for the first time for Tuva Republic.

***Rhaphium antennatum* (Carlier, 1835)**

RUSSIA – **Orenburg Reg.** • 3 ♂; Upper Dnieper, left bank of the Ural River above Orenburg; 5 Aug. 1934; L. Zimin leg.; ZISP RH2978.

Faunistic notes: from Murmansk Region to Astrakhan Region and for the North Caucasus. Recorded for the first time for Ural.

***Rhaphium appendiculatum* Zetterstedt, 1849**

RUSSIA – **Moscow Reg.** • 1 ♂; Abramtsevo; 15 Jun. 1958; E. Smirnov leg.; ZMMU DR00348.

Faunistic notes: from the Leningrad Region to the Crimea, from the North Caucasus and Altai. For the Moscow region, it was firstly noted by Fedchenko (1868).

***Rhaphium basale* Loew, 1850**

RUSSIA – **Krasnoyarsk Reg.** • 1 ♂; Lower Tunguska; 26 Jun. 1873; Chekanovsky leg.; ZISP RH3145.

Faunistic notes: Yakutia, Saratov Region. Recorded for the first time for Krasnoyarsk Region.

***Rhaphium boreale* Van Duzee, 1923**

RUSSIA – **East Sayans** • 2 ♂; Mondy, Arshan; 3 Jul. 1965; O. Negrobov leg.; VU 148-5143. **Khabarovsk Reg.** • 1 ♂; Vysokogorny; 13 Jul. 1974; A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-5210 • 1 ♂; Vysokogorny; 13 Aug. 1974; O. Negrobov leg.; VU 148-5214. – **Magadan Reg.** • 1 ♂; 24 km W Magadan, Sezheny village; 10 Jul. 1975, A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-5155. – **Amur Reg.** • 1 ♂; Zeya; 10 Jul. 1982, A. Ozerov leg.; ZMMU R00331. – **Taimyr Reg.** • 1 ♂; 100 km NOO Norilsk, Chopko River; 17 Jul. 1976; Yu. Chernenko leg.; VU 148-5156. – **Sakhalin** • 1 ♂; Urozhaynoye; 16 Jun. 1973; V. Logvinovsky leg.; VU 148-5213 • 15 ♂; outskirts of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk; 11 Aug. 1962; Shamshev leg.; VU 148-5223. – **Kamchatka** • 2 ♂; outskirts of Petropavlovsk-Kamchatski; 6 Jun. 1975; A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-5302 • 1 ♂; Ezzo, bank of Bystraya River; 27 Jun. 1975; A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-5334.

Faunistic notes: Holarctic northern species. From Russia it is known only from the Krasnoyarsk Region and Altai. Recorded for the first time for Sayan, Khabarovsk, Magadan and Amur Regions, Taimyr, Sakhalin, and Kamchatka.

***Rhaphium caliginosum* Meigen, 1824**

RUSSIA – **Crimea** • 1 ♂; Alushta Region, General village; 18 Aug. 1971; D. Kasparyan leg.; ZISP RH2884. – **Altai Reg.** • 1 ♂; Biysk; unspecified date; N. Fillipov leg.; ZISP RH3890.

Faunistic notes: from Murmansk Region to the North Caucasus and Krasnoyarsk Region. Recorded for the first time for the Crimea and Altai Territory.

***Rhaphium commune* (Meigen, 1824)**

RUSSIA – **Ural** • 1 ♂; Salekhard, Voikar River Basin; 15 Aug. 1925; V. Fridolin leg.; ZISP RH3717.

Faunistic notes: from Leningrad Region to the Crimea and the North Caucasus and Yakutia. Recorded for the first time for Polar Ural.

***Rhaphium confine* Zetterstedt, 1843**

RUSSIA – **Komi Republic** • 1 ♂; Vorkuta; 6 Jul. 1960; N. Chernov; ZISP RH3892 – **Ural** • 1 ♂; Salekhard, Sob' river basin; 27 Jun. 1925; V. Fridolin leg.; ZISP RH3721.

Faunistic notes: Murmansk Region and Taimyr. Recorded for the first time for Komi Republic and Polar Ural.

***Rhaphium dichromum* Negrobov, 1976**

RUSSIA – **Yaroslavl' Reg.** • 1 ♂; Beditsino; 14 Jul. 1907; A. Yakovlev leg.; ZISP RH2922.

Faunistic notes: from Leningrad Region to the North Caucasus and Crimea. Recorded for the first time for Yaroslavl' Region.

***Rhaphium discolor* Zetterstedt 1838**

RUSSIA – **Chelyabinsk Reg.** • 1 ♂; Magnitogorsk; 10 Aug. 1929; A. Plotnikov leg.; ZISP RH2950. – **Buryatia Republic** • 1 ♂; Peschanovka, Troitskosavsky Uyezd; 13 Jul. 1926; V. Mikhno leg.; ZISP RH2966. – **Irkutsk Reg.** • 1 ♂, Mamyр, Skufyin's trap; 22 Jul. 1953; A. Monchadsky leg.; ZISP RH2943 • 1 ♂; Dibi river; 7 Jul. 1900; A. Makerova leg.; ZISP RH2972. – **Khabarovsk Reg.** • 1 ♂; Vysokogorny; 8 May 1971; O. Negrobov leg.; VU 148-5144 – 2 ♂; Vysokogorny; 17 Jul. 1974; O. Negrobov leg.; VU 148-5145, 148-5146 • 1 ♂; Big Ussuri Island; 27 Jul. 1928; A. Stackelberg leg.; ZISP RH2952. – **Primorye** • 1 ♂; Rybolov Kamen'; 18 Jul. 1927; A. Stackelberg leg.; ZISP RH2957. – **Sakhalin** • 2 ♂; 25 km SW of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk, bank of the Lyutogi River; 13 Jul. 1982; I. Shamshev leg.; VU 148-5205 • 2 ♂; 29 km SW of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk, Urozhainoe; 13 Jul. 1982; I. Shamshev leg.; VU 148-5210 • 2 ♂; 20 km SW of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk, Dachnoye; 25 Jul. 1982; I. Shamshev leg.; VU 148-5216 • 1 ♂; 8 km N of Novo-Aleksandrovsk; 6 Jun. 1973; V. Logvinovsky; VU 148-5218 • 1 ♂; Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk; 15 Aug. 1973; V. Zlobin leg.; VU 148-5224.

Faunistic notes: from Murmansk, Leningrad and Magadan Regions and Primorye. Recorded for the first time for Chelyabinsk, Transbaikalia, Irkutsk, Khabarovsk Regions, and Sakhalin.

***Rhaphium dispar* Coquillett 1898.**

RUSSIA – **Sakhalin** • 1 ♂; 8 km N of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk; 13 Aug. 1982; I. Shamshev leg.; VU 148-5217 • 1 ♂; Harvest; 16 Jun. 1973; V. Logvinovsky leg.; VU 148-5227.

Faunistic notes: Primorye. Recorded for the first time for Sakhalin.

***Rhaphium elegantulum* Meigen, 1824**

RUSSIA – **Sverdlovsk Reg.** • 7 ♂; Nizhne-Tagilsky tract; 30 Jul. 1976; N. Muravyeva leg.; VU 148-5101, • 1 ♂; Verkhnyaya Salda; 14 Jun. 1976; N. Muravyova leg.; VU 148-5115 • 1 ♂; Salda River; 6 Jun. 1976; N. Muravyova leg.; VU 148-5108. – **Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Reg.** • 1 ♂; South Yamal, Khadyt River; 19 Jul. 1978; A. Tolstykh leg.; VU 148-5314. – **Irkutsk Reg.** • 1 ♂; Padun; 29 Jun. 1956; A. Monchadsky leg.; ZISP RH2974. – **Amur Reg.** • 1 ♂; Zeya; 2 Jun. 1981; A. Ozerov leg.; ZMMU R00324. – **Magadan Reg.** • 1 ♂; 12 km N Seymchan, river Seymchan; 27 Jul. 1975; A. Marshakov leg.; VU 148-5157.

Faunistic notes: from Murmansk Region to the North Caucasus, for Yakutia, Khanty-Mansiysk, Krasnoyarsk and Novosibirsk Regions. Recorded for the first time for Sverdlovsk, Irkutsk, Amur and Magadan Regions and for the Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Region.

***Rhaphium fasciatum* Meigen, 1824**

RUSSIA – **Yaroslavl' Reg.** • 1 ♂; Berditsino; 16 Jul. 1907; A. Yakovlev leg.; ZISP RH2923.

Faunistic notes: Leningrad Region, Yakutia, and Siberia (Frey, 1915). Recorded for the first time for Yaroslavl' region.

***Rhaphium fascipes* (Meigen, 1824)**

RUSSIA – **Taimyr Reg.** • 1 ♂; Lantakayskiy Kamen', Volchya; 6 Jul. 1967; L. Grunin leg.; ZISP RH3175. – **Ural** • 1 ♂; Salekhard, Sob' river basin; 25 Jul. 1925; V. Fridolin leg.; ZISP RH3725.

Faunistic notes: Leningrad and Moscow Regions, the North Caucasus and Krasnoyarsk Region. Recorded for the first time for Ural and Taimyr.

***Rhaphium flavilabre* Negrobov, 1979**

RUSSIA – **Sakhalin** • 1 ♂; Urozhaynoye; 21 Jun. 1973; V. Logvinovsky leg.; VU 148-5214 • 2 ♂; outskirts of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk; 7 Jul. 1982; I. Shamshev leg.; VU 148-5228 • 1 ♂; Aniva Region, Lyutanga river bank; 13 Jul. 1973; V. Logvinovsky leg.; VU 148-5231 • 1 ♂; Aniva Region, Lutanga river bank; 13 Jul. 1972; V. Zlobin leg.; VU 148-5244.

Faunistic notes: Primorye, Khabarovsk Region. Recorded for the first time for Sakhalin.

***Rhaphium glaciale* Ringdahl, 1920**

RUSSIA – **Altai** • 1 ♂; Ulagan Region, Kurai ridge; 3 Jul. 2008; A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-3895.

Faunistic notes: northern regions of Russia: Yakutia, Krasnoyarsk, Magadan, Murmansk and Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Regions, Buryatia Republic. Recorded for the first time for Altai.

***Rhaphium latimanum* Kahanpää 2007**

RUSSIA – **Komi Republic** • 1 ♂; Shel'yuar, Pechery floodplain; 12 Aug. 1978; K. Gorodkov leg.; ZISP RH3896. – **Ural** • 1 ♂; Voikar river basin; 8 Sept. 1925; V. Fridolin leg.; ZISP RH3723. – **Irkutsk Reg.** • 2 ♂; Bratsk Region, Krasny Yar; 8 Aug. 1954; I. Rubtsov leg.; ZISP RH2977, RH2978. – **Krasnoyarsk Reg.** • 3 ♂; Noril'sk; 6 Jul. 1977; A. Barkalov leg.; ZISP RH3146 • 12 ♂; Igarka; 5–27 Jul. 1971; V. Logvinovsky leg.; VU 148-5188. – **Primorye** • 1 ♂; Tigrovaya Pad'; 12 Jun. 1927; A. Stackelberg leg.; ZISP RH2958.

Faunistic notes: Khanty-Mansi, Yamalo-Nenets, Leningrad, Moscow, Khabarovsk and Magadan Regions, Yakutia and Taimyr. Recorded for the first time for Komi Republic, Polar Ural, Krasnoyarsk and Irkutsk Regions, and Primorye.

***Rhaphium longicorne* (Fallen, 1823)**

RUSSIA – **Ural** • 1 ♂; Salekhard, Voikar river basin; 20 Aug. 1925; V. Fridolin leg.; ZISP RH3722.

Faunistic notes: Leningrad and Murmansk Regions. Recorded for the first time for Ural.

***Rhaphium monotrichum* Loew 1850**

– **Kamchatka** • 1 ♂; Ust'-Bolsheretsk; 8 Aug. 1973; O. Negrobov leg.; VU 148-5318. – **Magadan Reg.** • 1 ♂; Olsk; 13 Jul. 1975; A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-5150. – **Primorye** • 1 ♂; Zheltaya river bank; 29 Jul. 1980; A. Sviridova leg.; VU 148-5913.

Faunistic notes: from Leningrad Region to the North Caucasus and Lake Baikal, Krasnoyarsk Region. Recorded for the first time for Smolensk and Yaroslavl' Regions, Buryatia Republic and Krasnoyarsk Region.

***Rhaphium nasutum* (Fallen, 1823)**

RUSSIA – **Komi Republic** • 1 ♂; Shchelyyur, Pechory; 12 Aug. 1978; K. Gorodkov leg.; ZISP RH3893. – **Sverdlovsk Reg.** • 1 ♂; Verkhnyaya Salda; 23 Jun. 1976; N. Muravyova leg.; VU 148-5104. – **Tyumen Reg.** • 2 ♂; Surgut; 25 Jul. 1977; K. Gorodkov leg.; ZISP RH3221. – **Irkutsk Region** • 1 ♂; Padun; 21 Jun. 1956; A. Monchadsky leg.; ZISP RH2951 • 7 ♂; Listvyanka; 24 Jun. 1965; O. Negrobov leg.; VU 148-5228. – **Krasnoyarsk Territory** • 4 ♂; Turukhansky Region, Igarka; 7 Jul. 1971; V. Logvinovsky leg.; VU 148-5182. **Mordovia Republic** • 3 ♂; Sosnovka; outskirts of Yavas; 8 Aug. 1980; D. Golubtsov leg.; VU 148-5374. – **Kamchatka** • 1 ♂; Kozyrevsk; 5 Jun. 1975; A. Bakalov; VU 148-5316. – **Sakhalin** • 3 ♂; Urozhaynoye; 16 Jun. 1973; V. Logvinovsky leg.; VU 148-5245; • 1 ♂; Aleksandrovsk-Sakhalin, Tymovsky; 19 Jul. 1982; I. Shamshev leg.; VU 148-5225.

Faunistic notes: middle and northern parts of the European part of Russia, Yakutia and Krasnoyarsk Region. Recorded for the first time for Sverdlovsk, Irkutsk, Krasnoyarsk and Tyumen Regions, Komi Republic, Mordovia Republic, Kamchatka and Sakhalin.

***Rhaphium nigribarbatum* Becker, 1900**

RUSSIA – **Tyumen Reg.** • 2 ♂; lower reaches of the Ob' River, Labytnangi; 7 Jul. 1973; V. Sychevskaya leg.; VU 148-5316. – **Taimyr Reg.** • 1 ♂, settlement Agapa, Pyasina; 7 Jul. 1967; K. Gorodkov leg.; ZISP RH3179. – **Komi Republic** • 1 ♂; Ust-Tsilma, Karpushevka; 11 Aug. 1978; K. Gorodkov leg.; ZISP RH3166 • 1 ♂; southern Yamal, Khadyta River; 19 Jul. 1978; A. Tolstykh leg.; VU 148-5236. – **Amur Reg.** • 1 ♂; Klimoutsy, 40 km W Svobodnyi; 18 Jun. 1959; L. Zinoviev leg.; ZISP RH2716. – **Kamchatka** • 1 ♂; Ust'-Bolsheretsk; 8 Aug. 1973; O. Negrobov leg.; VU 148-5318. – **Magadan Reg.** • 1 ♂; Olsk; 13 Jul. 1975; A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-5150. – **Primorye** • 1 ♂; Zheltaya river bank; 29 Jul. 1980; A. Sviridova leg.; VU 148-5913.

***Rhaphium patellitarse* Becker, 1900**

RUSSIA – **Sverdlovsk Reg.** • 1 ♂; Verkhnyaya Salda; 4 Jun. 1976; N. Muravyova leg.; ZISP RH3570. – **Krasnoyarsk Reg.** • 1 ♂; Dudinka; 10 Jul. 1977; A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-5186. – **Magadan Reg.** • 1 ♂; 24 km W of the village Snezhny; 10 Jul. 1975; A. Barkalov; VU 148-5158. – **Sakhalin** • 1 ♂; 28 km E Aleksandrovsk-Sakhalinsky; village Tymovsky; 19 Aug. 1982; I. Shamshevleg.; VU 148-5229 • 1 ♂; Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk; 14 Jun. 1955; V. Violovich leg.; ZISP RH2731.

Faunistic notes: Ural, Yakutia, Taimyr, Altai, Buryatia Republic and the Yamalo-Nenets Region. Recorded for the first time for Sverdlovsk, Krasnoyarsk and Magadan Regions and Sakhalin.

***Rhaphium richterae* Negrobov, 1977**

RUSSIA – **Sakhalin** • 1 ♂; Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk; 29 May 1956; V. Violovich leg.; ZISP RH2744 • 15 ♂; Novo-Aleksandrovsk; 6 Jun. 1973; V. Logvinovsky leg.; VU 148-5230–148-5245 • 3 ♂; Aniva Region, Urozhaynoye; 9–11 Jun. 1973; V. Logvinovsky leg.; VU 148-5206–148-5208; • 1 ♂; Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk; 08 Jun. 1973; V. Logvinovsky; VU 148-5211.

Faunistic notes: Kuril Islands. Recorded for the first time for Sakhalin.

***Rhaphium riparium* (Meigen 1824)**

RUSSIA – **Kamchatka** • 1 ♂; Petropavlovsk-Kamchatsky; 03 Jul. 1975; A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-5317.

Faunistic notes: from Leningrad Region to the North Caucasus, Yakutia and Krasnoyarsk Region. Recorded for the first time for Kamchatka.

***Rhaphium rivale* Loew, 1869**

RUSSIA – **Ural** • 1 ♂; Neroyka, Shakurya River; 6–8 Jul. 1990; A. Malozemov leg.; ZISP RH3731.

Faunistic notes: Leningrad and Krasnoyarsk Regions and Yakutia. Recorded for the first time for Ural.

***Rhaphium suavis* Loew, 1859**

RUSSIA – **Yaroslavl' Reg.** • 1 ♂; Berdicino; 17 Aug. 1998; A. Yakovlev leg.; ZISP RH2916. – **Adygea Republic** • 1 ♂; Kurdzhips; 23 Jun. 1963; O. Negrobov leg.; VU 148-5963.

Faunistic notes: Leningrad, Voronezh, Ryazan Regions and the North Caucasus. Recorded for the first time for Adygea and Yaroslavl Regions.

***Rhaphium tripartitum* Frey 1913**

RUSSIA – **Yamal-Nenets Autonomous Reg.** • 1 ♂; Yamal, village Kharasavey; 15 Aug. 1985; K. Gorodkov leg.; ZISP RH3810.

Faunistic notes: North of European part of Russia, Murmansk and Khanty-Mansi, Leningrad Regions and Yakutia. Recorded for the first time for Yamal.

***Rhaphium umbripenne* (Frey, 1915)**

RUSSIA – **Komi Republic** • 1 ♂; Scheljayur, Pechory; 12 Aug. 1978; K. Gorodkov leg.; ZISP RH3897. – **Kamchatka** • 1 ♂; Yelizovo, Avacha river bank; 13 Jun. 1975; A. Barkalov leg.; VU 148-5308. – **Ural** • 1 ♂; Polar Ural, Neroyka; 18–21 Jul. 1970; A. Malozemov leg.; ZISP RH3735.

Faunistic notes: The species was known from the northern regions of Russia, the Leningrad and Murmansk regions, Yakutia and the Khanty-Mansiysk Autonomous Region. It is a first record for the Komi Republic and Ural.

Conclusion

We presented new data on 28 *Rhaphium* species for the territory of Russia. *Rhaphium basale* Loew, 1850, *Rh. boreale*, *Rh. confine*, *Rh. dispar*, *Rh. fasciatum*, *Rh. flavilabre*, and *Rh. Longicorne* were recorded for the first time for one or two Russian regions. At present, there are 71 species of the genus *Rhaphium* known from Russia.

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